

A Transcultural Interrogation of Nepali Identity in India: Race, Ethnicity and Contemporary Literature

Paper Id : 18294 Submission Date : 07/11/2023 Acceptance Date : 16/11/2023 Publication Date : 20/11/2023

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DOI:10.5281/zenodo.10421447

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Abstract

The popularly accepted and practiced synonymy of the word Gorkha with Nepalese or Nepali though seemingly homespun is one of the crucial starting points of the discourse concerning the identity of the Indian Nepalis. A significant facet of the Gorkha identity in India was shaped by their recruitment in the British Indian Army, especially post the Anglo-Nepalese war of 1814-16. Prior to this, an intensively cultural and religious monarchical infiltration in Nepal under the rule of Prithvi Narayan Shah constructed an exclusive Hindu way of life. The language spoken was the Khas Kura (Nepali language) and only Hindu festivals were celebrated. The hierarchical caste system began to take root and the non-Hindus consisting of Gurungs, Newars, Tamangs and the like complied to it even as their ethnic identities were submerged as a result. Understanding the multifarious ways, which account for the Nepali population in India would require an attempt to identify the distinct phenomenon of migration, emigration and immigration with respect to time and space. The fairly recent birth of a collective identity among the Nepalis in India was cemented initially by the Hillmen's Association in 1907 demanding a separate administrative set up. The struggle for identity within the nation-state for these people gradually turned into a two-fold combat when the diverse social and cultural groups existing within the Gorkha community began to resurface, for unlike the forceful subjugation under Shah's rule in Nepal, India was a liberal home for the safe practice of their indigenous lifestyle. Identity formation is a constantly shifting amalgamation subject to temporal and spatial attributes.

Keywords Transcultural Interrogation, Nepali Identity, Race, Ethnicity, Contemporary Literature.

Introduction

The history of the Nepali community in India begins in media res. An attempt to locate the initiating point of the spatial movement of Nepalis into India reveals quite a few fountainheads. The regime of King Prithvi Narayan Shah in Nepal toward the middle of the 18th century which created the deep-rooted caste system and the founding of the Darjeeling Himalayan Railways and the tea estates providing employment to a vast number of workers are two of the familiar reasons. However, Prof. Tanka Bahadur Subba contends the idea that the migration of Nepalis to India happened around the mid-nineteenth century is wrong. There indeed is an uncharted territory of the unification of Nepal by Narayan Shah in 1786 before which the Darjeeling Hills and the floodplains of Doars region belonged to Sikkim and Bhutan successively. He defeated the Malla ruler expanding his dominion from Tista River in the east to Sutlej in the west including Northern Gangetic Plains and the Himalayas. However, it is the British recruitment of the Gorkha soldiers post the Anglo-Nepalese war in the British Indian Army which firmly established their identity within the colonially constructed confines of a martial race. The identity was attached to the body of the Gorkha by this very colonial discourse which was further embedded in history via the 'ethnographical writings' on the martial race.

Aim of study

In this paper author intends to reach a more streamlined understanding of the history behind the Gorkha Identity in India and to interrogate the subsuming of their ethnicity. Using trans culturalism as a method of penetrating the discourse, author will refer to contemporary Nepali literature in India and Nepal which plays a seminal role in cultural dissemination.

Review of Literature

Breaking free from this dominant form of representation requires intimation with the problem of double consciousness faced by the Gorkhas. 'The problem of double consciousness of the deterritorialized Gorkha subjectivity is torn between two seemingly conflictual impulses of a primordialistically constructed notion of the Gorkhajati (community) and the demands of a modern nation-state.' The fabric of the Gorkha community is unlike the one realized in Nepal under the reign of Narayan Shah; where he posited a Hindu way of living and the caste system began to take root which set the Bahuns (Brahmins) in the highest stratum of the society. This religious unification consequently reduced the non-Hindu and the non-Khas (Nepali language) speaking groups like Tamangs, Newars, Gurungs, Limbus to second class citizens in their own country. Each of these groups had their own unique languages and customs which were subsumed within the giant overhaul of the demands of a unified Gorkha kingdom. These diverse ethnic groups migrating to India from Nepal around the late 18th century embraced the umbrella identity of Nepali in India as well. The shared way of life in Darjeeling was significantly different from their neatly demarcated villages in Nepal and as many contemporary scholars say, a Tamang may not come across another Tamang but he will come across another Nepali like himself. The very many layers to the term 'Nepali' and the shared history of Nepal and India in this context along with the new surge for questioning established norms of identity make way for the need to constitute an interactive discourse. One is yet to find a cornerstone other than which the Britishers provided, 'A lot has been written about the short, broad chested, flat faced, snub-nosed men with their khukuris' (Golay 28-29).

The already conflicting grounds upon which identities lie in the modern world is further shaken up when its inherent plurality is bottlenecked with a single stand-for-all signifier. 'The difference in Ethnicity among the Nepali community in India and Nepal, can be attributed to the phenomenon where national identities shift into primary position for the individuals in relation to ethnic, caste and racial identities' (Gahatraj 31). Ethnicity is a comparatively new phenomenon in the academic scene, though the term itself has been in use in English language for a long time. In tandem with Stuart Hall's idea of identity as a continuing process subject to history and culture, the identity of the Nepalis in India needs to be reimagined. The problem with modernity is the predetermining power it invests upon history, heavily informed and affected by the colonial narratives, long after independence was achieved. The Gorkhas are portrayed as the race discovered by the British post their military performance in the Anglo-Nepalese war (1814-16) and it is within this perimeter that all discourses regarding their identity continue to emerge. This reductionist narrative curtails the acknowledgement of various social and cultural developments within the Nepali community. In addition to this, not all castes or tribes were included in the military recruitment; strict hierarchical caste system in Nepal rendered certain sects as ineligible and the British sought the Mongoloid race within the Gorkha community as the best fighters. The physical features were given an uncanny importance hence the popular notion of all Nepalis as having small eyes and high cheekbones stand.

Arianna Dagnino sees Transculturalism as 'a mode of reflective identity and a critical perspective that sees culture as relational webs and acknowledges the transitory, confluent, and mutually transforming nature of cultures. It is imperative to reflect upon the history of Nepalis in Nepal before situating their identity within India. The ethnic groups within the Nepali community i.e., Kiratas, Newaris and the Tagadharis had their own scripts and languages which were lost when they conformed to the dictates of Shah's Nepal where Nepali was an imposed language. The Nepali Diaspora comprises of the Tibeto-Burman Group. The percentage of the Nepali population with Nepali as their mother tongue was barely twenty percent and the rest were the previously mentioned ethnic and tribal communities who had their own languages. Despite this, all these different groups of people living adopted Nepali as the lingua franca because unlike having their own separate villages in Nepal the shared living scenario in India was significantly different. The ethnically hybrid community encountered a vast 'other' in India which brought the Nepali community together as a whole. The difference of traditions, customs and way of life within the people was sidelined and they embraced the Nepali language as a means of communication understood by all amongst them.

The term Gorkha does not have unanimity regarding its origins. Popular notions are of the term denoting a cluster of villages (Garkha is a Tibeto-Burman word which means the same), the writer Suryabikram Gyawali linked the term to the khas word garkha which meant revenue area; however, there is one interpretation of the term which raises concern. Gorkha, when deciphered as being a derivative of the term 'Go-rakkha' or the cow-protector undermines the existence of the practicing Buddhist sect within the community. The emphasis on a Hindu centred nation during the Rana regime is echoed when the government authorities take the liberty to define Nepali community as being essentially Hindu. The religious hegemony thus created isn't radically different from the authorial monarchy which happened in Nepal. The colonial narrative is worked on by the ones in power to serve the political demands of the nation. And because of the relative freedom the Nepalis experienced in India which was further realised by the mixed

marriages within various ethnic subgroups, the Nepali community came together as one with adoption of Nepali as their common language. The miniscule space occupied by them in the geo-political space of India made the educated members of the community realise the need of solidifying their identity if they were to make their demands met. This idea was materialised with the demand for a separate state which bore the slogans like, 'Lepcha, Bhutia, Nepali- hamisabaiGorkhali (Lepcha, Bhutia, Nepali- we all are Gorkhalis' (B.Subba).

Main Text